

ISSN Print: 2394-7500
ISSN Online: 2394-5869
Impact Factor: 5.2
IJAR 2019; 5(9): 312-317
www.allresearchjournal.com
Received: 16-07-2019
Accepted: 18-08-2019

Dr. Gurudatt Kakkar
Department of Commerce and
Management, Career Point
University, Kota Rajasthan,
India

Priya Shukla
Department of Commerce and
Management, Career Point
University, Kota Rajasthan,
India

Shalabh Shukla
Department of Agriculture
Science, Career Point
University, Kota, Rajasthan,
India

K Rathna
Department of Finance,
Himalayan University,
Itanagar, Arunachal Pradesh,
India

AC Tripathi
Chief Executive Officer,
Sanjeevani Foundation for
Health Education and
Environment Research Action,
New Delhi, India

Correspondence
Dr. Gurudatt Kakkar
Department of Commerce and
Management, Career Point
University, Kota Rajasthan,
India

Socio-economic survey of the respondents and their job satisfaction in Rajasthan University, Jaipur

Dr. Gurudatt Kakkar, Priya Shukla, Shalabh Shukla, K Rathna and AC Tripathi

Abstract

Job Satisfaction is the relationship between what everyone expects in accordance to what everyone achieves. A faculty in an Institute plays an important part in developing the knowledge and skills of youth. The research is designed that includes surveys, fact-findings, and inquiries from different groups. This study aims at investigating the socioeconomic survey of the respondents and their job satisfaction.

Keywords: Job satisfaction, socioeconomic, survey, respondents

Introduction

According Steven D. Brown, Robert W. Lent (2012) ^[1], job satisfaction refers to how well a job provides fulfilment of a need or want, or how well it serves as a source or means of enjoyment. Job satisfaction is defined more specifically in the literature, and several theorists have generated their own workable definitions. DeWayne P. Frazier (2009) ^[2] Job satisfaction is one of the most researched topics in the field of industrial psychology.

Role of faculty teachers in the society and in the education can change, but the importance of their position remains same. To attract and retain the quality faculty teacher is a great challenge with the educational institutions. In education, the essential quality of the teacher is to have a positive approach. Every teacher must have the potential and clear intention to discharge their duty with utmost devotion to derive satisfaction from their work.

Faculty job satisfaction levels seem to have direct bearing on the institutional as well as the student development and an understanding of job satisfaction, retention and employee turnover aspects of the faculties would help policy makers understand a very important organ of the society, responsible for future of the nation and generation.

Job satisfaction is the combination of emotional and psychological experience at any work. Job Satisfaction is the direct relationship between what everyone expects in accordance to what everyone achieves. Any work cannot be effectively done without satisfaction.

Most of the higher educational institutes throughout the country are suffering from acute shortage of faculty, not to mention good faculty members. To face faculty crisis, educational institutes opt for ad hoc, part time or visiting faculties who teach only for a few couple of hours. These faculties are least committed towards the institute; as they work in multiple places to make a living. They are thus frustrated and not motivated.

Job satisfaction is the state of feelings towards the job undertaken by an employee either positively or negatively. Job satisfaction is a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job ^[3]. It is an affective reaction to one's job ^[4]. It is also called an attitude towards one's job ^[5].

Teachers are important in building the nation and budding citizens of the nation. So, job satisfaction is an important concept that is not only related to an individual but it is relevant for the society's well-being. Job satisfaction is one factor that will ensure class performance and productivity of schools. The teachers would get interested to teach their students effectively when they are satisfied with their jobs ^[6]. Like India, other countries in the world are trying to improve their quality of education, so that it meets the demand of globalization. Alagbari (2003) who found out that the satisfying factors were salary, achievement, relationships with teachers, compatibility between qualifications, experience and work, social

status and job security [7]. Teachers would perform to maximum capacity, only if they are satisfied with their jobs. The job satisfaction is an important phenomenon in every sector especially in the teaching profession. The present paper aims to survey the status of the respondent's and their job satisfaction in Rajasthan.

Methodology

Site selected for the study was self-financing Arts and Science Colleges affiliated to Rajasthan University, Jaipur (Figure 1).

Fig 1: Map of Rajasthan

Research Design: The research is designed that includes surveys, fact-findings, and inquiries from different groups. In order to retain objectivity every attempt was made to take an unbiased sample. The study is a combination of both exploratory and descriptive one in nature. A well-structured questionnaire was prepared for considering workplace conditions and calculating the level of job satisfaction among the teaching faculty of self-financing Arts and Science Colleges, affiliated to Rajasthan University, Jaipur.

Result and Discussion

The site was surveyed and data was collected insight into the socio-economic condition of the respondents and their job satisfaction level towards the dimension. Given below table-1 is gender wise classification of the respondents.

Table 1: Gender wise classification of the respondents

S. No	Gender	No of the respondents (N=400)	Percentage (100)
1	Male	223	55.75
2	Female	177	44.25

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 223 respondents are men which constitutes 55.75%, whereas, 177 respondents are women constituting 44.25% (Figure 2).

It is observed that men are found to be working at the highest percentage in the Self-financing Arts and Science Colleges than women. Because of male respondents are

highly motivated towards the flexible working times and immediate employment opportunities. Further it offers better social recognition than any other professions.

Fig 2: Gender wise classification of the respondents

Table 2: Age wise classification of the respondents

S. No	Age Group	No of the respondents (N=400)	Percentage
1	Below 30 yrs	120	30
2	31 to 35 yrs	131	32.75
3	36 to 40 yrs	61	15.25
4	41 to 45 yrs	64	16
5	46 yrs & above	24	6

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows that 131 respondents are in the age group of 31 to 35 years constituting 32.75%. And 30% of the respondents belong to the age group of below 30 years. 16% of the respondents belong to 41 to 45 years. 15.25% of them belong to 36 to 40 years and the lowest 6% of them belong to 46 years and above.

It is clear that 62.75% of the respondents lie in the age group of below 35 years and the age group of above 36 years is showing decreasing trend.

Fig 3: Age wise classification of the respondents

Table 3: Marital status of the respondents

S. No	Marital Status	No of the respondents (N=400)	Percentage
1	Married	234	58.5
2	Unmarried	166	41.5

The above table reveals that 234 respondents are married constituting 58.5%. There are 41.5 % of the respondents who are unmarried.

Fig 4: Marital status of the respondents

Table 4: Educational qualifications of the respondents

S. No	Educational Qualification	No of the Respondents (N=400)	Percentage (100)
1	PG only	165	41.25
2	M.Phil	183	45.75
3	Ph.D	43	10.75
4	NET/SET	9	2.25

The above table indicates that 45.75 % of the respondents have completed both PG degree and Master of Philosophy courses; 41.25% of the respondents are PG degree holders; 10.75 % of the respondents have Doctorate degree and 2.25 % of the respondents have qualified themselves with NET / SET examinations.

It is observed that 46.25% teachers who are holding PG with M.Phil degree are easily admitted in the self-financing Arts and Science colleges.

Fig 5: Educational qualification of the respondents

Table 5: Experience wise classification of the respondents

S. No	Experience	No of the respondents (N=400)	Percentage (100)
1	Below 2 yrs	178	44.5
2	3 to 4 yrs	110	27.5
3	5 to 6 yrs	75	18.75
4	7 yrs & above	37	9.25

The above table replicates that 44.5% of respondents have got work experience of less than 2years, followed by 27.5% of them belonging to 3 to 4 years, 18.75 % of them belonging to 5 to 6 years of experience and 9.25% of them belonging to 7 years & above category. Thus, it is very much clear that the highest (44.5 %) of the respondents are with less than 2 years of experience, and the lowest

percentage of the respondents (9.25%) with the experience of 7years and above.

Therefore, it is observed that teachers of self-financing colleges leave the job from one college to another college owing to poor salary structure, no salary increment and threatening by the Administrators / Management not to do any higher studies further.

Fig 6: Experience classification of the respondents

Table 6: Course/ Branch wise classification of the respondents

S. No	Course	No of the respondents (N=400)	Percentage (100)
1	Arts	221	55.25
2	Science	179	44.75

The above table discloses that 221 respondents belong to Arts Category which constitutes 55.25% and 181 respondents belong to science constituting 44.75%.

Fig 7: Course/branch wise classification of the respondents

Table 7: Discipline / Department wise classification of the Respondents

S. No	Course	Department	No. of the respondents (N=400)	Percentage (100)
1	Science	Bio-technology	28	7
2		Comp science	78	19.5
3		Mathematics	47	11.75
4		Industrial Electronics	6	1.5
5		Physics	28	7
6	Arts	Hindi	37	9.25
7		English	55	13.75
8		Commerce	90	22.5
9		Economics	15	3.75
10		Management	16	4

The above table reveals that the core subjects are taught by the respondents among whom 22.5% of the respondents belong to the Commerce department and 19.5% of them belong to computer Science, 13.75% of them belong to English, 9.25% of them belong to Tamil, 11.75% of them

belong to Mathematics, 7% of them belong to Bio-Technology, 4% of them belong to Management, 1.5% of them belong to Industrial Electronics, 7% of the them belong to Physics and 3.75% of them belong to Economics department.

Fig 8: Discipline / Department wise classification of the Respondents

Table 8: Income wise classification of the respondents

S. No	Income Group	No of the respondents (N=400)	Percentage (100)
1	Below Rs. 6000	226	56.5
2	Rs. 6001 to Rs 8000	113	28.25
3	Rs. 8001 to Rs. 10000	34	8.5
4	Rs.10001 & above	27	6.75

The above table indicates that 56.5% of the respondents are earning a monthly income of less than Rs.6000. There are 28.25% of the respondents earning a monthly income between Rs.6001 and Rs.8000, and only 6.75% of the respondents are earning above Rs.10001. It is obvious that the very lowest percentage (6.75%) of the respondents is earning a monthly income above Rs.10001. The highest percentage (56.5%) of the respondents is earning a monthly income of less than Rs.6000. Therefore it is observed

Fig 9: Income wise classification of the respondents

The table-9 represents the cross tabulation on various dimensions of job satisfaction

Table 9: Various dimensions of job satisfaction

Gender	N	Various Dimensions of job satisfaction							
		Workplace Conditions		Compensation		Infrastructure		Professional Development	
		High	Low	High	Low	High	Low	High	Low
Male	223	100 (44.8)	131 (58.7)	120 (53.8)	107 (47.9)	104 (46.6)	123 (55.1)	97 (43.4)	130 (58.2)
Female	177	92 (51.9)	77 (43.5)	57 (32.2)	116 (65.5)	65 (36.7)	108 (61.01)	98 (55.3)	75 (42.3)

Workplace conditions

The highest (58.7%) percentage of the male respondents is the least satisfied towards the workplace conditions and the remaining 44.8% of the respondents are highly satisfied with workplace conditions, whereas the highest (51.9%) percentage of the female respondents are highly satisfied and 43.5% of the respondents have low satisfaction.

Compensation

The highest (53.8%) percentages of the male respondents are highly satisfied and 47.9% have low satisfaction. Similarly, 65.5% of the female teaching faculty have low satisfaction and the remaining 32.2% of the faculty highly are satisfied with the compensation.

Infrastructure

Of all, 55.1% of the male respondents are little satisfied and 46.6% of the them are highly satisfied.61.01% of the female respondents have low satisfaction and 36.7% of them have high satisfaction towards the infrastructure.

Professional Development

Among the total respondents, 58.2% of the male respondents have low satisfaction and 43.4% of the respondents have high satisfaction and 42.3% of the female respondents have low satisfaction and 55.3% of the respondents have high satisfaction towards professional development.

Table 10: Cross tabulation between the age and various dimensions of job satisfaction

Age Year	N	Various Dimensions of job satisfaction							
		Workplace Conditions		Compensation		Infrastructure		Professional Development	
		High	Low	High	Low	High	Low	High	Low
Below 30	120	78 (65)	42 (35)	61 (50.8)	59 (49.1)	64 (53.3)	56 (46.6)	70 (58.3)	50 (41.6)
31 to 35	131	57 (43.5)	74 (56.4)	52 (39.6)	79 (60.3)	50 (38.1)	81 (61.8)	73 (55.7)	58 (44.2)
36 to 40	61	21 (34.4)	40 (66.6)	28 (45.9)	33 (54.1)	28 (45.9)	33 (54.1)	28 (45.9)	33 (54.1)
41 to 45	64	27 (42.1)	37 (57.8)	29 (45.3)	35 (54.6)	26 (40.6)	38 (59.3)	21 (32.8)	43 (67.1)
46&above	24	7 (29.1)	17 (70.8)	5 (20.8)	19 (79.1)	7 (29.1)	17 (70.8)	9 (37.5)	15 (62.5)

The above tables indicate that the highest 65% percentage of the respondents belong to the age category of below 30 years, and have high satisfaction towards Workplace conditions. And the (55.7%) respondents who are in the age group 31 years to 35 years are highly satisfied towards the professional development. (45.9%) of the respondents who

are in the age group between 36 and 40 years, are highly satisfied with the compensation and infrastructure. (42.1%) of the respondents in the age group of between 41 and 45 years are highly satisfied with the Workplace conditions and (37.5%) of the respondents in the age group of 46 years and above are satisfied with the professional developments.

Table 11: Cross tabulation between the marital status and various dimensions of job satisfaction

S. No	Marital	N	Various Dimensions of job satisfaction							
			Workplace Conditions		Compensation		Infrastructure		Professional Development	
			High	Low	High	Low	High	Low	High	Low
1	Married	234	87 (37.1)	147 (62.8)	123 (52.5)	111 (47.4)	81 (34.6)	153 (65.3)	107 (45.7)	127 (54.2)
2	Unmarried	166	101 (60.8)	65 (39.1)	58 (34.9)	108 (65.1)	88 (53)	78 (46.9)	96 (57.8)	70 (42.1)

The above table indicates that 62.8 % of the married respondents have low satisfaction towards the Workplace conditions. 52.5% of the respondents showed high satisfaction towards compensation. 65.3% of the respondents were in low level of satisfaction towards infrastructure. And 54.2% of the respondents were in low level of satisfaction towards professional development. With

regard to the unmarried respondents, 60.8% were in high level of satisfaction towards Workplace conditions; 65.1% of the respondents were at low satisfaction towards compensation; 53% of the respondents were highly satisfied with the infrastructure and 57.8% of the respondents were in high level of satisfaction towards the professional development.

Table 12: Cross tabulation for the educational qualification of the respondents and their various dimensions of job satisfaction

S No	Education	N	Various Dimensions of job satisfaction							
			Workplace Conditions		Compensation		Infrastructure		Professional Development	
			High	Low	High	Low	High	Low	High	Low
1	PG	165	83 (50.3)	82 (49.6)	90 (54.5)	75 (45.4)	59 (35.7)	106 (64.2)	81 (49.1)	84 (50.9)
2	M. Phil	183	88 (48.1)	95 (51.9)	78 (42.6)	95 (51.9)	103 (56.2)	80 (43.7)	100 (54.6)	83 (45.3)
3	Ph. D	43	19 (44.1)	24 (55.8)	8 (18.6)	35 (81.3)	5 (11.6)	38 (88.3)	16 (37.2)	27 (62.7)
4	NET/SET	9	5 (55.5)	4 (44.4)	7 (77.7)	2 (22.2)	2 (22.2)	7 (77.7)	5 (55.5)	4 (44.4)

The above table represents the influence of educational qualification towards the various dimensions of the job satisfaction of the teaching faculty. The respondents having PG degree only are satisfied in high level with the compensation which constitutes 54.5%. 56.2% of the respondents having PG with M.Phil were in high level of satisfaction towards the infrastructure facilities. 44.1% of the respondents having Ph.D as the highest qualification were in high level of satisfaction towards the Workplace conditions. 77.7% of the respondents having SET/NET qualification were in high level of satisfaction towards the Workplace conditions and professional development.

Conclusion

Job satisfaction is the fulfilment of one’s expectation from job. It is a pleasurable or positive emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one’s job experience. But the expectation of people may not be homogeneous. It may differ from person to person, place to place, job to job, context to context, and organization to organization. So, job satisfaction cannot be generalized. From the academic perspective, Workplace conditions, compensation,

infrastructure and professional development affect the job satisfaction of the teaching faculty.

The present study has tried to discover the level of job satisfaction among the teaching faculty of self-financing Arts and Science colleges considering the four dimensions namely Workplace conditions, compensation, infrastructure and professional development. The study shows that Workplace conditions, professional development and infrastructure significantly creates overall job satisfaction of the teaching faculty, strategic attention need to be given specifically for the compensation dimension which is closely associated with overall job satisfaction. Formation of consortium at the state level would be the best choice to exercise compensation dimension with reasoning.

This study has made an important contribution to the self-financing Arts and Science colleges to understand the job satisfaction level among the teaching faculty and help to increase the satisfaction level so as to retain good employees and ensure increase in the performance of the teaching faculty.

Hence, the evidence from the quantitative data of this study shows that the teaching faculty need good Workplace conditions especially management support, defining its

employment conditions, improved infrastructure and compensation.

References

1. Steven D, Brown Robert W, Lent Career Development and Counselling: Putting Theory and Research to Work; John Wiley & Sons, 2012, 720.
2. DeWayne Frazier P. Job Satisfaction of International Educators Universal-Publishers, 2009.
3. Brief AP, Weiss HM. Organizational behaviour: affect in the workplace; Annual Review of Psychology. 2001; 53:282.
4. Weiss HM. Deconstructing job satisfaction: separating evaluations, beliefs and affective experiences; Human Resource Management Review. 2002; 12:174.
5. <http://m.timothy-judge.com/documents/Jobattitudes.pdf>
6. Nigama K *et al.* Job satisfaction among school teachers; International Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics. 2018; 119(7):645-2655.
7. Alagbari A. Job satisfaction among a sample of general education head teachers in the Eastern Region of Saudi Arabia; Journal of Gulf and Arabic island studies. 2003; 29:169-197.